

A STUDY ON EMPLOYEE ABSENTEEISM: STUDY AT SENTHIL PLASTIC CONTAINERS VIRUDHUNAGAR

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Abstract:

The article entitled on worker's absenteeism is expected to decide the workers condition, compensation, amenities provided, participation, inspiration strategies and advancements. The motivation behind this article is to audit on issues of workers. Absenteeism is a type of withdrawal conduct apart from turnover. Workers not going to work when scheduled can be a significant issue for disassociations and turnover. This article intends to identify and distinguish the most well-known reasons for employee absence on management cost. Worker absence is a serious issue for the executives since it includes significant importance. Absenteeism is one of the widest spread deterrents to usefulness, productivity and seriousness. Workers badgering by employers or the board is one of the justifications behind absenteeism. The reactions might be affected by isolated inclination Workers not going to work when listed can be a significant issue of the disassociation. The article comprises of objectives, constraints, research approach, findings, thoughts and conclusion. The data required for the examination has been accumulated from essential and auxiliary information.

Key Words: Absenteeism, Turnover, Workers, Employers, Causes Of Employee Absenteeism

Introduction:

Absenteeism is defined as the failure of the worker to report for work when he is 'scheduled to work. A worker is expected to work when the employer has work available for him and the worker is aware of it. Authorized absence is also treated as absence while presence even for a part of the shift is treated as presence for the whole shift. Absence on account of strikes, lockout, layoff, weekly rests or suspension is not taken into account. Thus, it relates to only voluntary absence due to personal reasons of the individual concerned. Absenteeism rates given in the report represent percentage of man days lost due to absence to the corresponding total man days scheduled to work. The man days scheduled to work is arrived at by adding the man day's actually worked and the man days lost on account of absence of the workers due to some reason or the other.

A worker who reports for any part of a shift is to be considered as present. An employee is considered scheduled to work when the employer has work for him there is no reason to expect well in advance that the employee will not be available for work at the specific time. An employee on regularly scheduled vacation is, therefore, not to be considered as employer-ordered layoff. On the other hand an employee who requests time off at other than a regular vacation period should be considered as absent from scheduled work until he returns, or until it is determined that the absence will be such duration that his name is removed from the list of active employees. After this date he should be considered as neither scheduled to work nor absent.

Similarly, an employee who quits without notice should be considered as absent from scheduled work until his name is dropped from the active list, but preferably this period should not exceed one week in either case. If a strike is in progress, workers on strike should be considered as neither scheduled to work nor absent, since data on time is lost because strikes are collected under the head of man days lost on account of industrial dispute.

The Reasons for Absenteeism:

The phenomenon of absenteeism has been explained in various ways. The atmosphere prevailing in a plant, therefore, affects His attitude to his work, and either persuades him to attend regularly or keeps him away. Irritating uncertainty, irregularity, and confusion in the factory are likely to be important cause of absenteeism. The attitude and practice of the management also contribute to absenteeism

Causes of Absenteeism:

- Maladjustment with factory conditions
- Social religious ceremonies
- Unsatisfactory housing conditions
- Industrial fatigue
- Unhealthy working conditions

- Absence of adequate welfare facilities
- Alcoholism
- Indebtedness
- Improper and unrealistic personnel policies
- Inadequate leave facility

Measures for Control Absenteeism:

- Adoption of a well-defined recruitment procedure
- Cordial relationship between supervisors and workers
- Provision of reasonable wages and allowances and job security for workers
- Motivation of workers and social measures
- Improved communication and prompt redressal of grievances
- Liberal grant of leave
- Safety and accident prevention
- Provision of healthy and hygienic working conditions
- Development of workers education

About the Company:

Senthil Plastics Container Virudhunagar in the year 2006 and engaged in the manufacture of plastic paint pails of various sizes and other injection molded components as per customer specification and molds. The company has a modern and state of the art manufacturing facility to develop the products on understanding the customer need for quality performance and application, translate the need into product chemistry, develop cost effective value added product. The company's products are widely used by large, medium and small industries throughout the country. The main aim of Senthil Plastics Container Virudhunagar is to satisfy the customers by providing supplier service and quality products. The organization implemented ISO 9001: 2008 Quality Management System integrated with other applicable standards and systems to assure effective production and quality of products as well as enhancing customer satisfaction. They are one of the emerging manufacturers and suppliers of high quality injection molded components. They supply the products across various industries like Paint, Lubricant, Inks and Dyes, Food, Agro, Pharmacy, Domestic Household Usage, etc. They strictly follow the QCDS concept in their business which helps to grow continuously.

Objectives of the Study:

- To find out the various reasons for absenteeism in the study unit.
- To suggest the controlling measures to reduce employee absenteeism.
- To know the impact of absenteeism on organizational performance.

Need of the Study:

Absenteeism has become a major problem in almost all the industrial sectors. Excessive absenteeism constitutes a considerable cost to the industry even when the absent employee receives no pay. Because of disorganization of work, work schedules are upset and delayed, resulting in the management failure to meet delivery dates. When sick pay is authorized, the cost of absenteeism mounts up more rapidly. It is, therefore, desirable that measures are effectively implemented to minimize the cost of absenteeism as far as possible. In the light of various factors promoting excessive rate of absenteeism in the units concerned, measures will have to be taken by the management.

Scope of the Study:

- Each and every industry has a certain rate of absenteeism due to their own family circumstances and unavoidable circumstances they take leave. This will affect the productivity, growth and sales in the industry.
- To avoid this condition we can motivate the worker by taking classes on specific topic like motivation and providing leave benefits to the employees.
- To help the organization to reduce their job turnover.
- The study tries to find out solution to overcome absenteeism problem.

Hypothesis of the Study:

- Null Hypothesis H_0 : There is no significance relationship between the Monthly income and Satisfaction level of present wages.
- Alternative Hypothesis H_1 : There is significance relationship between the Monthly income and Satisfaction level of present wages.

Research Design:

The research design constitutes the blue print for the collection, measurement and analysis of data. There are types of research design; they are exploratory research design, experimental research design and describe and diagnostic research design. The research had adopted descriptive research design for the study.

Research Methodology:

Research methodology is a way to systematically solve research problem. Research methodology is

understood as a source of the study how to research is done scientifically. The various steps adopted by a researcher in studying the research problem along with the logic.

Sample Design:

A sample is a subset from the total population. A sample is a subset from the total population. It refers to the techniques or the procedure to the research would adopt in selecting items for the sample (i.e) the size of the sample.

Details of Population:

The study was conducted on the employees of Madurai.

Population Frame:

- The data was collected from the company manpower portfolio.
- This includes the list of 120 respondents (refer to the analysis of data).

Sampling Method:

Sampling method utilized was convenience sampling was adopted.

Methodology of the Data Collection:

A descriptive research was undertaken to the study of the problem. The study is descriptive in nature. Descriptive research is those which are concerned with describing the characteristics of a particular individual of a group. The descriptive research describes the demographic the characteristic of the respondents and is typical concern with determining frequency with something occurs how the variables vary together.

Sources of Data:

- Primary Data: It was collected through questionnaire further this data, are processed and tabulated using graphs the tables where analyzed and the finding has been drawn accordingly.
- Secondary Data: It refers to a special kind of ratio, it is used to make comparison between two or more series of data, since the percentage reduce everything to a common base and there by allow meaningful comparison be made.

Tools Used for Research:

- Simple Percentage Method
- Chi - Square Test
- Correlation

Suggestions:

- From the study, the factors that influencing the employees' absenteeism is due to either health problem or personnel reasons. So, the organization may arrange a counseling program by the experts either from outside or inside the organization.
- Organization may frequently arrange meetings/trainings/outings/other recreational activities to their employees to increase the interaction with supervisors and organization may show their care to their employees by simply listening to them.
- Organization may retain the experienced persons to improve the organization performance or productivity by providing salary hike or revising their increment period.
- The employees are made to understand the high impact of their absenteeism in the productivity of the organization during the meetings and training programs to avoid their absenteeism.
- Have an employee wellness program. A modern wellness program should address not just the physical but also the emotional needs of your employees. If you have a wellness program, it can significantly reduce your employee absenteeism. A wellness program doesn't have to necessarily be expensive to be effective.
- Offering flexible work hours when possible.
- Empowering employees. Empowered employees who feel like they have control over their work environment are going to be better overall in terms of performance and attendance.
- Allow employees to feel comfortable sharing their feedback and ideas, and let them work in ways that they enjoy as long as the work itself is getting done.

Conclusion:

The research entitled "Employees absenteeism" in Senthil Plastics Container reveals the importance of their best human resources within the organization. This study helps to identify the factors affecting employee's absenteeism like family issues, child health condition, personal problem etc. This study also helps the employee's awareness about the absenteeism effects on employees' performance and organizations' productivity. This study also helps the organization to identify the employee's expectations to reduce the absenteeism which will help the development of employees and the organization.

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